

Cubosome lipid nanocarriers for delivery of ultra-short antimicrobial peptides

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Hypothesis: Although antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are a promising class of new antibiotics, their inherent susceptibility to degradation requires nanocarrier-mediated delivery. While cubosome nanocarriers have been extensively studied for delivery of AMPs, we do not currently understand why cubosome encapsulation improves antimicrobial efficacy for some compounds but not others. This study therefore aims to investigate the link between the mechanism of action and permeation efficiency of the peptides, their encapsulation efficacy, and the antimicrobial activity of these systems.

Experiments: Encapsulation and delivery of Indolicidin, and its ultra-short derivative, Priscilicidin, were investigated using SAXS, cryo-TEM and circular dichroism. Molecular dynamics simulations were used to understand the loading of these peptides within cubosomes. The antimicrobial efficacy was assessed against gram-negative (*E. coli*) and gram-positive (MRSA) bacteria.

Findings: A high ionic strength solution was required to facilitate high loading of the cationic AMPs, with bilayer encapsulation driven by tryptophan and Fmoc moieties. Cubosome encapsulation did not improve the antimicrobial efficacy of the AMPs consistent with their high permeation, as explained by a recent 'diffusion to capture

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model'. This suggests that cubosome encapsulation may not be an effective strategy for all antimicrobial compounds, paving the way for improved selection of nanocarriers for AMPs, and other antimicrobial compounds.

1. Introduction

The discovery of penicillin by Sir Alexander Fleming was a turning point in history, saving countless lives and revolutionising medicine [1]. However, he cautioned against the overuse of antibiotics in 1945, warning that the “public will demand [the drug and] ... then will begin an era ... of abuses” [2]. As described by the World Health Organisation (WHO), antibiotic resistance currently represents one of the biggest threats to global health and food security [3]. Antibiotic-resistant bacteria including gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria (Fig. 1) have now been detected in every country in the world and their rapid emergence is a major threat to the efficacy of currently available antibiotics [4,5]. The pipeline in development of new antibiotics is inadequate due to the lack of financial incentives and technical challenge of developing successful antibiotics. Investing in antibiotic development is considered high risk for pharmaceutical companies because of minimal financial gain and high rate of failure [6,7]. There is, therefore, an urgent need to investigate new classes of antimicrobial agents.

One potential alternative to conventional small molecule antibiotics is antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which are an integral part of the innate immune defence mechanism of most organisms including humans, animals and plants [8]. AMPs are generally short peptides (10–50 amino acids) with an overall positive charge of +2 to +9 [9]. They exhibit advantages such as broad spectrum killing against a wide variety of organisms and are less likely to result in bacterial resistance [10–12]. The antimicrobial lipopeptide Daptomycin, derived from the organism *Streptomyces roseosporus*, has been FDA approved as an antibiotic since 2003 [13,14]. However, AMPs have major limitations as drugs, including poor chemical and physical stability, which have impacted their clinical translation. Natural AMPs are susceptible to chemical and enzymatic degradation *in vivo*, resulting in low oral absorption [10,15–17]. They can have high manufacturing costs and many display high toxicity in mammalian cells [18,19].

One approach to improve their efficacy as pharmaceuticals is to combine AMPs with a drug delivery vehicle such as a lipid nanocarrier (NCs) [11]. There has been extensive research on using a wide variety of lipid nanocarriers including liposomes, nanoemulsions, solid lipid

nanoparticles, and nanostructured lipid carriers [20,21]. Recently, several research studies assessed lipid nanocarriers of internal cubic symmetry (cubosomes) for the delivery of small molecule antibiotics [22–24] and peptides [25–29].

Cubosomes are nanostructured particles generally ranging from ~100–300 nm in size, formed from dispersion and steric stabilisation of the bulk cubic phase [30,31]. Their structure consists of a single bilayer which is separated by two continuous, unconnected aqueous regions. The three different bicontinuous cubic phases known to form cubosomes include the diamond (Q_{II}^D) phase with crystallographic space group Pn3m, the primitive (Q_{II}^P) phase with crystallographic space group Im3m, and the gyroid (Q_{II}^G) phase with crystallographic space group Ia3d, Fig. 2 [29,32,33]. Due to their amphiphilic internal nanostructure, cubosomes can accommodate a wide range of different drugs including small molecule drugs, peptides, proteins and RNA-based therapeutics; with hydrophilic drugs contained within the aqueous networks and hydrophobic drugs within the lipid bilayer region [34–39]. Loading of amphiphilic or hydrophobic peptides such as AMPs is facilitated by the high interfacial bilayer surface area of approximately 400 m²/g [39,40]. Cubosomes offer many additional advantages as drug delivery vehicles for peptides, most notably protection from enzymatic degradation [27,41]. A unique advantage of cubosomes for delivery of antimicrobials is their ability to exhibit fusogenic properties with cellular membranes that can improve their uptake into bacteria, particularly gram-negative bacteria [42].

Several studies have demonstrated the potential of using cubosomes as nanocarriers for antibiotic delivery. Encapsulation of the antibiotic amoxicillin trihydrate in monoolein (MO, Fig. 3. (c)) cubosomes resulted in a greater antibacterial effect towards *S. aureus*, a gram-positive bacterium, compared to unloaded amoxicillin, while being non-toxic to dermal fibroblast cells [22]. An ocular formulation of MO cubosomes containing the antibiotic vancomycin (used to treat gram-positive bacteria) was shown to be an effective method to treat bacterial keratitis in rabbits, with improved pharmacokinetics compared to the vancomycin solution and with effective relief of keratitis symptoms after 120 hr [43]. A polytherapy approach, combining polymyxin B with unloaded cubosomes, was also shown to be an effective antimicrobial strategy

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the cell wall of (left) gram-positive bacteria and (right) gram-negative bacteria.

(compared to loaded polymyxin B cubosomes) [23]. Cubosomes have additionally been shown to be effective against intracellular infections such as tuberculosis [24]. The use of cubosomes as nanocarriers resulted in improved efficacy against intracellular *P. aeruginosa* for tobramycin DDAB lipid nanoparticles and for vancomycin-loaded lipid nanoparticles against intracellular SCV *S. aureus* [44].

A range of research studies have investigated cubosomes as nanocarriers for AMPs, including AP114 [25,27], LL-37 [25,27], DPK-060 [25,27], Gramicidin A' [28], Melittin [28], Indolicidin [28], Alamethicin [28], Cecropin A' [28], and Pexiganan [28]. However, the antimicrobial activity of AMPs encapsulated in cubosomes varies widely between different studies. Incorporation of AP114 and LL-37 in MO cubosomes did not significantly improve activity (relative to the unloaded peptide) against a variety of bacteria including *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and MRSA. One exception was DPK-060; a reduction in the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was observed against *E. coli* by 1–2 dilutions. For the peptide LL-37 the antimicrobial efficacy was not enhanced in MO cubosomes but was augmented in micelles and vesicles, indicating nanostructure plays a role [45,46]. Moreover, MO vesicles in the absence of stabiliser (F127) have also shown improved antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* [46]. Nevertheless, these formulations did not display significant antimicrobial activity against gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis* and *B. subtilis*) [46] indicating the ongoing challenge in treating gram-positive bacteria. Similarly, encapsulation of AMPs such as Alamethicin, Gramicidin A' and, Cecropin A' in MO cubosomes did not improve activity against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. cereus* or *S. aureus*. The lipid composition was demonstrated to play an important role in the uptake, toxicity, and antibacterial activity of the AMPs, with the lipid phytantriol shown to have improved efficacy for the delivery of Alamethicin to *B. cereus* [28]. Overall, there is a gap in the literature in understanding why cubosome encapsulation improves the antimicrobial activity of some AMPs but not others.

Herein, we investigate the use of cubosomes for the encapsulation of the well-known AMP Indolicidin (Fig. 3. (a)), as well as Priscilicidin (Fig. 3. (b)), an ultra-short peptide fragment derived from Indolicidin. Indolicidin is derived from bovine neutrophil blood cells and has demonstrated efficacy against a wide range of gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria [47]. This AMP is rich in tryptophan residues, containing five within its amino acid sequence [48], which have been shown to be important for its membrane association and, therefore, mechanism of action [49–53]. The ultra-short peptide fragment Priscilicidin, which includes a combination of aromatic tryptophan and cationic arginine residues covalently linked to a fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl (Fmoc) group (Table 1), was derived from Indolicidin using rational design principles [54]. The simple design and ultra-short nature of Priscilicidin allows it to be produced more quickly and cost effectively, while retaining the advantages of naturally occurring AMPs. A previous study by us has shown that a range of AMPs, based on Indolicidin, with sequences as short as 2–5 amino acids can exhibit antimicrobial activity [54]. Of the 20 ultra-short fragments tested, Priscilicidin was found to have strongest antimicrobial activity as a hydrogel, exhibiting potent antibacterial and antifungal activity against a range of

Fig. 3. Chemical structures of (a) Indolicidin, (b) Priscilicidin, and (c) Monoolein.

bacterial and fungal strains including methicillin resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and *C. albicans* [54].

Indolicidin and Priscilicidin were encapsulated within monoolein (MO) cubosomes at varying concentrations (1, 2, 5 mol%). Cubosomes were formulated both in Milli-Q water and in the presence of salt (150 mM NaCl) which has been shown previously to enhance the loading of cationic peptides [28]. The encapsulation efficiency was assessed using Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS). The particle

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the different cubosome morphologies; the diamond (Q_{DI}^D) on the left, the primitive (Q_{PI}^D) phase in the middle, and the gyroid (Q_{GI}^D) phase on the right.

Table 1

The peptide properties for Indolicidin and Priscilicidin.

Peptide properties			
Peptide sequence	Length # amino acids	Net charge at pH 7	% Hydrophobic amino acids
Indolicidin ILPWKWPWWPWRR-NH ₂	13	+3	77 %
Priscilicidin Fmoc-WWRR-NH ₂	4	+2	60 %

morphology, size and zeta potential were characterised with a combination of cryogenic-transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM) and dynamic light scattering (DLS). Synchrotron Small angle X-ray Scattering (SR-SAXS) was used to determine the internal nanostructure within the lipid nanoparticles. The secondary structure of the encapsulated peptides was characterised using Synchrotron Radiation Circular Dichroism (SRCD). Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations were performed to study the interactions between the peptides and a MO bilayer. Finally, the antimicrobial efficacies of encapsulated Indolicidin and Priscilicidin were compared to those of the corresponding unencapsulated peptide against *E. coli* and MRSA strains using an MTS assay.

2. Materials and Methods

Monoolein (MO) (99 %, Nu-Chek Prep), Indolicidin (98.36 %) and Fmoc-WWRR-NH₂ (96.36 %, Priscilicidin) (ChemPep), Pluronic F127 (Sigma Aldrich), sodium chloride (99.7 %, Sigma Aldrich), sodium fluoride (≥ 99 %, Sigma Aldrich) 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol (≥ 99 %, Sigma Aldrich), chloroform (≥ 99.8 %, Sigma Aldrich), and ethanol (99.5 %, AR, Univar) were all used without further purification. Grenier half-area 96 well SAXS plates (product code 675101) were purchased from Interpath Services.

2.1. Cubosome preparation

Cubosomes were prepared by first co-dissolving the lipids and peptide in solvent (ethanol for cubosomes without peptide added; 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol for samples with peptide added) at an appropriate ratio, followed by evaporation of the solvents under vacuum. The resulting lipid or lipid/peptide mixtures were hydrated using F127 solution in Milli-Q water or 150 mM NaCl solution and then dispersed using probe sonication (40 % amplitude (52 W), pulsing in cycles for 3 s on / 5 s off for a total of 3 min).

The pH of MO lipid NCs stabilised with F127, dissolved in Milli-Q water has been measured previously by us using a Mettler Toledo bench-top pH meter. The pH value of Milli-Q water and 5 mg/mL F127 solution were measured as 5.7 and 5.6 respectively [55].

The AMPs Indolicidin or Priscilicidin (detailed in Table 1), were loaded into the cubosome formulations with increasing concentration (1, 2, and 5 mol%). All cubosome formulations were prepared at 5 wt% (50 mg) of lipid in 1 mL solution with 0.5 wt% of F127 solution. AMP-cubosome formulations with salt were prepared with 0.5 wt% of F127 dissolved in 150 mM NaCl.

2.2. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements

SAXS experiments were conducted at the SAXS/WAXS beamline at the Australian Synchrotron, with a beam wavelength of $\lambda = 1.12718 \text{ \AA}$ and using a Pilatus 2 M detector. The distance between the sample and detector was 1600 mm with a corresponding q-range of $0.026 - 0.86 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. The samples were transferred into sealed Grenier 96 well microplates and mounted directly in the beam path. Each sample was recorded with an automated scan for an exposure time of 1.0 s and at a temperature of 25 °C. Silver behenate was used as a calibration standard. The scattering

images were integrated using the ScatterBrain software. The SAXS data were analysed using Python software to identify the phase and lattice parameters of the cubic lipid nanoparticles. Using python coding, the Bragg reflections were detected as peaks and automatically fit to determine the phase according to the expected lattice spacings. To improve the peak detection the data was corrected using an alternating least squares (als) baseline in the python code. The lattice parameter (a) of the cubic phases were derived from the Bragg peaks detected in the X-ray diffraction patterns. The assigned peaks were fitted using the relationship shown in equation (1), where q is the peak position along the scattering vector axis, and h, k, and l are the Miller indices of the respective cubic lattice. The 1D scattering plot of an empty well from the Grenier 96 well plate is provided in Fig. S1.

$$q = \frac{2\pi}{a}(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

2.3. Cryo-TEM

An FEI Vitrobot was used to vitrify the nanoparticle samples for imaging with cryo-TEM. The samples were dripped onto lacey carbon copper mesh grids and vitrified rapidly in liquid ethane with a humidity of 95 %, blot force of 4 and a blot time of 4 s. The samples were imaged using an FEI Tecnai F30 Transmission Electron Microscope operating at 300 kV with a Gatan 626 cryo-transfer specimen holder, at a defocus level of -5 \mu m to -8 \mu m .

2.4. Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

DLS measurements were performed on a Zetasizer-APS (Malvern, UK) at 25 °C. The samples were diluted to 1/25th of their original concentration in Milli-Q water and were run in triplicate which were averaged to determine their average particle size (Z-average) and polydispersity (PDI). The refractive indices used for MO and water were 1.46 and 1.33, respectively.

2.5. Zeta potential

Zeta potential measurements were performed using a Zeta potential-Zetasizer-Nano ZS (Malvern, UK) at the PC2 lab in the Micro Nano Research Facility (MNRF) at RMIT University, Melbourne. The cubosomes were diluted to 1/25th of their original concentration in 2 mM KNO₃ solution. The zeta potential was recorded using polystyrene zeta potential cells (Malvern) at 25 °C. The refractive indices used for MO and water were 1.46 and 1.33, respectively.

2.6. MTS based cell viability assay on *E. Coli* O157:H7 and MRSA

2.6.1. Material

Pure cultures of gram-negative *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli* O157:H7) and gram-positive methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA clinical strain) were obtained from the microbial culture collection of RMIT University, Australia. Bacterial strains were maintained in nutrient broth (NB) (CM0001 Oxoid, ThermoFisher Scientific) and nutrient agar (NA) (Sigma Aldrich, Australia). Syringe filters (0.45 μm , PES) were purchased from Millipore, Australia. Sterile Technoplas Petri Dishes were purchased from Interpath Services, Australia. The MTS assay kit (Promega CellTiter 96 Aqueous One Solution) was purchased from Promega.

2.6.2. Cell viability assay

The MTS assay kit, a colorimetric assay, was used to determine cell viability, based on the mean value for the activity of mitochondrial succinate dehydrogenase [56]. The bacterial cells (*E. coli* O157:H7, MRSA) were cultured in sterilised and autoclaved NB medium (made as per standard instructions, 13 g/L (pH 7.4), which contains 5 g/L (86

mM sodium chloride) within a 20 mL sterile plastic screw cap glass vial with an optical density ($O.D_{600}$ used to measure the bacterial growth) of 0.5–0.6 and grown at 37 °C with shaking at 150 rpm. Each cell viability determination assay against the bacterial strain was performed in triplicate for all sets of samples. Each set contained either the neat peptide (Indolicidin or Priscilicidin) or peptide-loaded nanoparticles. Cubosome samples were loaded immediately prior to use. Neat peptide stock solutions were prepared in Milli-Q water or 150 mM NaCl. 1 % bacterial inoculum was added to both Milli-Q water and to 50 µg/mL MO-based lipid nanoparticles as controls. The peptide loaded and unloaded MO nanoparticles were filtered using sterile Millex-GP syringe filters (0.45 µm, PES, Millipore) and used for these experiments. Either a stock solution of the free peptide (at the same concentrations as for cubosomes to keep volumes consistent) or peptide loaded lipid nanoparticles at an appropriate concentration were added at the time of inoculation to the 1 mL of culture (with 1 % inoculum) medium and incubated for 20–24 h, at which time the bacterial growth reaches the stationary phase at 37 °C with shaking at 150 rpm.

From each sample 100 µL of cell culture medium was taken and loaded into a 96 well plate. Bacterial cell viability was measured using the MTS assay kit and 10 µL of MTS solution was added per 100 µL of sample and incubated for 10 min at 37 °C. A microplate reader (SpectraMax, Molecular Devices) was used to measure the OD absorbance at 490 nm to assess the cell viability. MO mixed with the MTS solution (no bacteria) gave rise to background signals and were thereby subtracted from bacterial sample readings. The measured absorbance from the control sample was set to 100 % cell viability. All other sample data were therefore adjusted relative to this value and used to calculate the % inhibition

2.7. Peptide encapsulation efficiency

The peptide AMP loading within the lipid nanoparticles was quantified first by separating the unloaded peptide from the loaded peptide via centrifuge filtration using an Amicon-Ultra filter with a 100 kDa molecular weight cut-off for a total of 20 min at 5000 g. Using 250 µL vial inserts (Agilent), the samples were loaded into HPLC vials in 100 µL aliquots and then quantified using Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS) (RMIT University, Melbourne, AUS). The system was equipped with an Agilent Eclipse XDB-C18, 5 µm 4.6 x 250 mm column operated at room temperature. A flow rate of 1 mL/min was employed using a mobile phase A composed of 0.1 % formic acid in Milli-Q and mobile phase B composed of acetonitrile, ACN) for Indolicidin and a flow rate of 0.2 mL/min for Priscilicidin for the same solvent conditions. A linear gradient was run as follows: 70 % of solvent A and 30 % of solvent B to start, until at the 10th minute we reached 45 % of solvent A and 55 % of solvent B, and at the 15th minute 5 % of solvent A and 95 % solvent B. We maintained a ratio of 5 % of solvent A and 95 % of solvent B until the 25th minute and then finished with 70 % solvent A and 30 % solvent B at 28 min with a stop time of 5 min to finish. The injection volume was 10 µL and the absorbance was measured at 220 nm for both peptides. Peptide concentration was determined using a calibration curve for each peptide (shown in Fig. S2., Supporting information). The peptide encapsulation efficiency was determined using equation (2).

Encapsulation efficiency (%) = 100

$$\times \frac{[\text{total peptide}] - [\text{unbound peptide}]}{[\text{total peptide}]} \quad (2)$$

Statistical analysis was performed for the encapsulation efficiency of the samples, using the GraphPad Prism software using unpaired two-tailed Student t-tests with Welch's correction.

2.8. Circular dichroism (CD)

Synchrotron radiation-circular dichroism measurements were conducted at the AU-CD beamline of the ASTRID2 Synchrotron radiation facility in Aarhus, Denmark. Samples were analysed using quartz cells with a ~ 0.1 mm path length, with the correct pathlength accurately (<1 µm) determined for each cell by an interference technique [57] and the CD data were collected in the 180 – 330 nm range. The sample temperature was maintained at ~ 25 °C. For all samples the data were recorded with a 1 nm step size, with a dwell time of 2 s/pt. For unloaded peptides, samples were analysed by averaging 3 scans as well as for the corresponding reference baseline with a slit opening of 60 µm (normal operating conditions). Cubosome samples were averaged over 6 scans with a nearly 3 times larger slit opening due to the high levels of light scattering and absorbance of the lipids within the sample. The spectra of the samples and reference baselines were each smoothed using a 7-point (for samples) or 13-point (for baselines) Savitzky-Golay filter. The CD signals were normalised for the cubosome samples with the corresponding free peptide. The theoretical schematic representation of the exciton phenomenon (Fig. 7. (c)) is based on equation (3) below, where A represents the amplitude of the curve, μ is centre position of the peak in terms of wavelength, σ is the width of the peak, and x is wavelength. The positive and negative cotton effects in this figure are positive and negative gaussian curves with the mid-points shifted, one positive and one negative. The values used for the positive cotton effect is an A of 1, μ of 115 nm and σ of 15 nm. The values used for the negative cotton effect is an A of -1, μ of 135 nm and σ of 15 nm. The bisignate curve is the sum of both positive and negative cotton effects. The wavelength of the figure is from 50 – 200 nm at 2 nm steps.

$$f(x) = A \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

2.9. MD simulations

Monoolein bilayer construction and simulation: The structure and the parameters of the MO lipid molecule were obtained using the LipParGen server [58–60]. A simulation was also performed to obtain an equilibrated structure of a MO bilayer. MD simulations were all performed using GROMACS 2023 and the OPLS-AA force field [61–64]. A single molecule of MO was contained in a cell of 5.6 x 5.4 x 4.8 nm³ and a total of 4,719 water molecules were added into the simulation box using the TIP4P water model [65]. A time step of 2 fs and the Linear Constraint Solver (LINCS) algorithm were implemented for the simulation [66]. The cut-off for the Coulombic potential was set to 1.2 nm and the smooth particle mesh Ewald (PME) method was used to study the electrostatic interactions [67]. The steepest descent protocol was adopted to perform the energy minimization of the system for a maximum of 100,000 steps. The temperature for the equilibration and production simulations was set to 310 K. The system was first equilibrated under the constant particle number, velocity, and temperature (NVT) conditions for 200 ps. Subsequently, the constant particle number, pressure, and temperature (NPT) ensemble was implemented to perform another 200 ps equilibration simulation. In both ensembles, the Berendsen thermostat and barostat were applied [68]. The equilibrated lipid molecule was then contained in a subcell and duplicated to form the top leaflet of the MO bilayer. Subsequently, the bottom leaflet was constructed by reproducing these subcells. Each bilayer was composed of 12 x 12 subcells, resulting in a total of 144 molecules of MO that were placed in random orientations. A production simulation was performed using the assembled bilayer. The temperature coupling for this simulation was applied with the velocity rescale thermostat and the time constant was set to 0.1 ps [69]. The structure of the bilayer was extracted from the simulation using the Visual Molecular Dynamics 1.9.3 software [70–72].

Peptide-bilayer interaction simulations: The structure of Indolicidin

(PDB ID: 1G89) was obtained from the Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics Protein Data Bank (RCSB PDB) and prepared using VMD [70–72]. Priscilicidin was constructed using Swiss-PdbViewer (Deepview) and Discovery Studio Visualizer [73,74]. The Indolicidin and Priscilicidin were placed above the bilayer at a height of ~ 0.21 nm and 0.26 nm, respectively, with respect to the minimum peptide-bilayer distance. A simulation cell of $7.7 \times 6.8 \times 9.7$ nm³ was also established for both simulations. The Parrinello-Rahman barostat and the semi-isotropic pressure coupling were used to maintain the pressure of the system at 1 bar [75]. The Indolicidin-MO system contained a total of 11,209 TIP4P water molecules, 46Na⁺ and 50Cl⁻ counter ions were added to achieve a salt concentration of 150 mM. Similar solvation and ion addition protocols were used for the Priscilicidin-MO system, where 9,983 water molecules, 46Na⁺, and 48Cl⁻ counter ions were added. Both systems were equilibrated using the NVT ensemble, followed by the NPT ensemble for 200 ps each. Subsequently, 200 ns production simulations were performed using the temperature and pressure coupling schemes mentioned above. The simulated trajectories were visualized using the VMD software.

3. Results

3.1. Peptide encapsulation efficiency (EE)

The encapsulation efficiency (EE) was determined for both

Indolicidin (Indol.) and Priscilicidin (Prs.) in MO cubosomes, both in Milli-Q water and in 150 mM NaCl, which has been previously shown to enhance the loading of charged peptides [28].

In the absence of salt, the EE of Indolicidin (1 mol%) in MO cubosomes (Fig. 4. (a)) was ~ 32 %, consistent with a previous study [28]. The encapsulation efficiency for Priscilicidin at 1 mol% was significantly higher at ~ 73 % ($p = 0.0091$). Addition of 150 mM NaCl significantly improved the encapsulation efficiency for both peptides, to ~ 96 % for Indolicidin ($p = 0.0146$) and ~ 99 % for Priscilicidin ($p = 0.016$) compared to peptides in Milli-Q water. The improved loading upon addition of salt has been previously observed for a range of AMPs in cubosomes and is presumed to be due to the increased ionic strength of the solution which screens repulsion between the cationic peptides facilitating increased loading [28].

3.2. Particle internal morphology, particle size and zeta potential

The phase adopted by the cubosomes, and its associated lattice parameter (LP), were investigated following encapsulation of both AMPs using Synchrotron small-angle X-ray scattering (SR-SAXS). A plot of LP as a function of mol% of peptide is provided in Fig. 5. (a). Representative 1D SAXS plots of intensity vs q are provided in Fig. 5. (b and c) for encapsulated Indolicidin, and Fig. 5. (d and e) for encapsulated Priscilicidin. The average particle size and zeta potential for all particles is provided in Table 2.

Fig. 4. (a) The encapsulation efficiency % (EE) for Indolicidin and Priscilicidin loaded cubosomes (1 mol%) with and without salt (150 mM NaCl) and (b) the methodology. Statistical analysis shown using unpaired two-tailed Student t-tests with Welch's correction. * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, **** < 0.0001 , ns represents not significant.

Fig. 5. (a) SAXS lattice parameters of MO cubosomes loaded with Indolicidin (Indol.) and Priscilicidin (Prs.) at varying mol% concentrations (1, 2, and 5 mol%) with and without salt (150 mM NaCl). Note: * represents a possible coexistence of phases with the second phase unidentified. In some cases, the error bars are too small to be visible. (b) 1D SAXS patterns of intensity vs scattering vector q for MO cubosomes containing Indolicidin at 1, 2 and 5 mol% in Milli-Q water. (c) 1D SAXS patterns of intensity vs scattering vector q for MO cubosomes containing Priscilicidin at 1, 2 and 5 mol% in Milli-Q water. (d) 1D SAXS patterns of intensity vs scattering vector q for MO cubosome containing Indolicidin at 1, 2 and 5 mol% in 150 mM NaCl and, (e) 1D SAXS patterns of intensity vs scattering vector q for MO cubosomes containing Priscilicidin at 1, 2 and 5 mol% in 150 mM NaCl.

Table 2

The particle size, zeta potential and particle morphology of the MO nanoparticles with Indolicidin or Priscilicidin incorporated. Data are provided in Milli-Q water and in the presence of 150 mM NaCl. Note: * mixed phase.

Pep. (mol%)	MO					MO NaCl (150 mM)			
	Size (nm ± nm)	PDI	Zeta (mV±mV)	Å ± Å	Phase	Size (nm ± nm)	PDI	Å ± Å	Phase
–	239 ± 6	0.13	−1.0 ± 0.1	140 ± 0	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m	347 ± 0.1	0.21	141 ± 0	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m
Indol. (1)	137 ± 2	0.25	15.5 ± 0.2	128 ± 5	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m	455 ± 29	0.15	143 ± 1	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m
Indol. (2)	145 ± 30	0.38	27.0 ± 0.3	–	–	521 ± 20	0.16	165 ± 2	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m
Indol. (5)	110 ± 0	0.31	36.2 ± 0.6	–	–	266 ± 61	0.19	–	–
Prs. (1)	160 ± 5	0.24	11.1 ± 0.02	129 ± 0 *	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m *	254 ± 11	0.11	130 ± 0	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m
Prs. (2)	150 ± 9	0.28	17.1 ± 0.6	–	–	315 ± 13	0.18	134 ± 1	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m
Prs. (5)	128 ± 4	0.31	33.5 ± 1.9	–	–	224 ± 38	0.18	184 ± 7	Q_{II}^P ; Im3m

At 25 °C the MO control sample (in the absence of peptide) adopted a primitive Q_{II}^P phase with a lattice parameter of 139 Å, in good agreement with the literature [76]. Sharp Bragg peaks in the ratio $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{4}$, $\sqrt{6}$ are observed in Fig. 5. (b), consistent with a well-structured Q_{II}^P cubic phase. However, encapsulation of Indolicidin resulted in almost complete disruption of the underlying cubic nanostructure, even at the lowest concentrations studied. Following encapsulation of Indolicidin at 1 mol %, Bragg peaks in the ratio $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{4}$, $\sqrt{6}$ may still be observed but these are very weak and poorly defined, suggesting the introduction of significant disorder within the sample with the loss of most ordered cubosomes. By 2 mol% loading the cubic phase structure was destroyed with no Bragg peaks observed in the SAXS patterns for 2 mol% or 5 mol % loading. DLS data confirm a decrease in the average particle size from 235 nm (for pure MO cubosomes) to particles in the range 110 – 135 nm for Indolicidin-loaded lipid particles, consistent with a phase transition of most lipid particles to vesicles or other unstructured lipid nanoparticles. This was confirmed by cryo-TEM images at 1 mol% Indolicidin (Fig. 6. (b)) showing a majority of unstructured vesicles present with no cubosome-like particles observed. A combination of very weak Bragg peaks in the SAXS pattern, and the absence of cubosomes in the cryo-TEM images, suggests that the number of residual cubosome particles at 1 mol% Indolicidin is extremely low. In the absence of Indolicidin, MO cubosomes demonstrate near neutral zeta potential of -0.9 mV shown in Table 2. This increased following Indolicidin encapsulation in a concentration-dependent manner, reaching a maximum zeta-potential of 36.6 mV at 5 mol% loading of Indolicidin, Table 2.

A similar structural analysis was carried out for particles in the presence of 150 mM NaCl, Fig. 5. Addition of salt did not significantly affect the phase formed by pure MO cubosomes, with retention of a Q_{II}^P phase of lattice parameter 140 Å. However, the addition of salt appears to facilitate retention of the cubic phase to much higher peptide loadings; clear Bragg peaks in the ratio $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{4}$, $\sqrt{6}$, were observed up to 2 mol% Indolicidin. The lattice parameter of the Q_{II}^P phase increased with increasing Indolicidin concentration with measured lattice parameters of 142 Å at 1 mol% and 165 Å at 2 mol% Indolicidin. These observations could be explained by negative hydrophobic mismatch between the hydrophobic span of the peptide and the width of the lipid bilayer, similar to the effect observed previously for WALP peptides in cubosomes [77]. However, by 5 mol% Indolicidin Bragg peaks have disappeared indicating the absence of cubic structure in the particles. The average particle size for MO in salt (347 nm) was slightly larger than that of MO cubosomes (235 nm). For Indolicidin-loaded cubosomes at 1 and 2 mol% the average cubosome size increased to 435 nm and 535 nm, respectively. However, by 5 mol% loading, a decrease in particle size to 223 nm was observed, commensurate with the loss of the cubosome structure and, presumably, the formation of unstructured, vesicle-like particles.

The structural response of the cubosomes to Priscilicidin loading was very similar to that observed for Indolicidin, despite the much smaller size of this peptide fragment. At 1 mol % Priscilicidin, weak and poorly defined Bragg peaks are observed with spacing $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{4}$, $\sqrt{6}$ implying that Priscilicidin disrupts the cubic Q_{II}^P architecture of the lipid MO (Fig. 5. (a) and (d)). We note that the intensity distribution of the Bragg peaks (the $\sqrt{4}$ peak is more intense than expected) is consistent with the Q_{II}^P phase coexisting with another, currently unidentified, phase. At higher Priscilicidin loadings of 2 and 5 mol%, no Bragg peaks are observed, commensurate with complete loss of the cubic nanostructure within the particles. This is associated with a decrease in the average particle size to 131–163 nm, consistent with a phase transition to vesicle-like structures. Cryo-TEM micrographs (Fig. 6. (c)) confirm the presence of a majority of vesicles, with retention of some cubosome-like particles. Fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis was performed on MO cubosomes (Fig. 6. (a)) and cubosomes loaded with 1 mol% Priscilicidin (Fig. 6. (c)). The extracted lattice parameters (145 Å for MO and 136 Å for Priscilicidin loaded cubosomes) are in good agreement with the SAXS data. The zeta potential of loaded-Priscilicidin particles became

increasingly positive with increasing peptide concentration, reaching a maximum of 34.9 mV at 5 mol% Priscilicidin, Table 2.

Similarly to Indolicidin, the presence of 150 mM NaCl facilitated retention of the cubic phase to higher Priscilicidin loadings. A Q_{II}^P phase was retained at all concentrations (1, 2, 5 mol%) of Priscilicidin in MO NaCl cubosomes with clear Bragg peaks in the ratio $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{4}$, $\sqrt{6}$ at 1 and 2 mol%, and weaker but still identifiable Bragg peaks at 5 mol%. The LP of the Q_{II}^P phase for Priscilicidin at 1 and 2 mol% loading were 130 Å and 133 Å, respectively, which is considerably lower than that seen for Indolicidin-loaded cubosomes in the presence of salt, and lower than the LP for pure MO cubosomes in the presence of 150 mM NaCl (140 Å). This effect is presumably due to the shorter hydrophobic span of Priscilicidin, which results in negative hydrophobic mismatch between the peptide and the lipid bilayer. This has been previously shown to promote an increase in negative curvature of the bilayer, and associated decrease in the lattice parameter [77]. In contrast to this trend, we note that by 5 mol% loading the lattice parameter has increased significantly to 180 Å suggesting possible swelling of the cubic phase at very high concentrations of Priscilicidin which we are currently unable to explain. The size of the Priscilicidin-loaded cubosomes was in the range 247–324 nm, similar to that of pure MO cubosomes in 150 mM NaCl and as expected for cubosome structures.

3.3. Peptide secondary structure

The CD spectra of Indolicidin and Priscilicidin were obtained at the SRCD beamline (AU-CD) at the ASTRID2 facility, Aarhus University, Denmark. Spectra were obtained for peptides either solubilised in Milli-Q water, in salt (150 mM NaF) or loaded in MO cubosomes at 1 mol% and are presented in Fig. 7. NaF was used in place of NaCl due to the strong absorption of Cl^- below 200 nm [78]. The CD spectrum of Indolicidin dissolved in Milli-Q water is characterised by a large negative band at ~ 200 nm, consistent with an unordered structure as previously described in the literature (Fig. 7. (a)) [51,72]. A similar spectrum consistent with a disordered structure was obtained for Indolicidin in a NaF salt solution. The CD spectrum of Indolicidin encapsulated within MO cubosomes remains mostly unchanged except for the appearance of an additional small negative band at ~ 230 nm. We suggest that this band results from bilayer encapsulated Indolicidin, with the relatively low intensity consistent with poor encapsulation efficiency. With the presence of NaF and a corresponding increase in encapsulation efficiency, the Indolicidin band at ~ 230 nm dramatically increases in intensity as previously observed for Indolicidin loaded in MO cubosomes in the presence of potassium fluoride (KF) [28]. This additional band has been previously attributed to the tryptophan side chains, specifically changes in the Indole chromophore, for Indolicidin bound to POPC/POPG vesicles [51,72,79]. This change is in agreement with high membrane association of the peptide in the MO bilayer in line with the high encapsulation efficiency of the peptide and retention of the cubic phase as shown by SAXS data [28].

Due to the very short nature of the Priscilicidin peptide, the spectrum in Milli-Q water is not associated with any secondary structure (α -helix, β -strand, or disordered structure) related to that found in the literature [80]. However, in the presence of salt, a significant change to the CD spectrum was observed, with the appearance of a large positive peak at ~ 230 nm and a negative band at ~ 208 nm (Fig. 7. (b)) characteristic of the exciton coupling phenomenon between the two arginine residues. The higher ionic strength associated with the 150 mM NaF sample presumably allows the two arginine groups to approach more closely than in the presence of Milli-Q water (where the cationic charge causes electrostatic repulsion). The close proximity of the identical arginine chromophores results in exciton coupling leading to the observed bisignate curves (positive and negative cotton effects), as shown in Fig. 7. (c) which combine to form a bisignate spectrum (sum) characteristic of exciton coupling. This occurs when the electronic transitions of the chromophores are excited to excitonic states (X' and X''),

Fig. 6. Cryo-TEM Images of (a) MO reference sample, (b) MO-Indolicidin (1 mol%) loaded cubosomes, and (c) MO-Priscilicidin (1 mol%) loaded cubosomes. All samples shown are in Milli-Q water. Inserts: Fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis for ordered particles MO and MO Prs (1 mol%).

Fig. 7. Circular dichroism spectra of (a) Indolicidin, (b) Priscilicidin as freely dissolved peptides in both Milli-Q and NaF (150 mM) and within MO and MO salt cubosomes (cubosomes diluted down to 5 mg/mL), (c) a theoretical schematic representation representing the bisignate curves that arise from exciton coupling.

observed here for arginines, and these excitonic states respond differently to right- and left-circularly polarised light [81].

Priscilicidin encapsulated in MO and MO salt cubosomes exhibits similar exciton coupling to that of Priscilicidin freely dissolved in NaF as shown in Fig. 7. (b). There is no significant difference in the CD spectra between the two cubosome formulations for Priscilicidin possibly due to higher encapsulation efficiencies compared to Indolicidin.

3.4. Molecular interactions of Indolicidin and Priscilicidin with a MO bilayer

Molecular dynamics simulations of Indolicidin and Priscilicidin interacting with a MO bilayer were carried out to provide an improved understanding of the inter-relationship between the peptide and the lipid bilayer, and potentially help explain the antibacterial studies [82–84]. The number of contacts formed by these peptides with a MO bilayer, as well as the peptides' radii of gyration (Rg) as a measure of their compactness, root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) as a measure of the flexibility of the residues, and insertion into the MO bilayer were analysed.

The number of contacts, derived from the MD simulations, revealed that insertion of Indolicidin into the MO bilayer is driven by the tryptophan residues, specifically tryptophan Trp8 and Trp9 (Fig. 8. (a)). The minimum distances between these two tryptophan residues and the MO bilayer, extracted from 40 ns to 200 ns of the trajectory, demonstrated that these residues were generally found closer to the MO bilayer than the other residues, Table 3. This observation is consistent with other studies published in the literature, highlighting that hydrophobic residues are the main contributors in the interactions of Indolicidin with both zwitterionic and anionic lipid bilayers [50,85]. In general, the tryptophan residues (with the exception of Trp6) maintained a stable distance from the bilayer, unlike the other residues of Indolicidin (Fig. S3, Supporting Information). In line with this observation, Trp6 also made the least contact with the lipid bilayer and its minimum distance was the highest among all five tryptophans of the peptide (Fig. 8, Table 3 and Fig. S3 & S4). Residues Arg13 and Lys5 had the least interactions with the MO bilayer and were positioned furthest away from the bilayer (Fig. 8. (a) and Table 3). The Z-coordinates of the centre of mass (COM) of the peptide residues and the glycerol headgroup of the top leaflet were extracted from the trajectory to evaluate the insertion of the residues into the lipid bilayer (Fig. 11. (c & d)). Consistent with the observation discussed above, Trp8, Trp9, and Trp11 embedded deeper and more frequently into the bilayer, whereas Trp6 only occasionally inserted into the hydrocarbon chain of the lipid. As expected, this analysis also revealed that the arginine residues were predominantly positioned away from the lipid bilayer. These observations were confirmed by the snapshots taken from different timepoints of the trajectory, highlighting that the tryptophans were attracted to the bilayer while the arginines favoured the aqueous phase (Figs. 9 and 11).

The average Rg of Indolicidin interacting with the MO bilayer was determined to be 0.78 ± 0.03 nm (Fig. 8. (b)) throughout the 200 ns trajectory. The Rg of Indolicidin displayed a sudden drop at 14 ns followed by a gradual decrease but remained relatively stable after 60 ns of the simulation. We infer that Indolicidin underwent some structural changes during the first 20 ns of the simulation, but its structure gradually became more stable towards the end of its trajectory. Consistent with the Rg calculations, the RMSF data (Fig. 8. (c)) showed that Indolicidin exhibits a low level of flexibility, with Trp4 and Trp9, and the three proline residues restricting the peptide flexibility. The RMSF analysis is consistent with a previous study highlighting that the C-terminal half of Indolicidin (residues 8 – 13) was generally more flexible than the N-terminal half (residues 1 – 7) [86]. The rigidity of proline has also been discussed in a previous study [87].

Unlike Indolicidin, the interactions between Priscilicidin and the MO bilayer were predominantly driven by the Fmoc moiety and tryptophan residues (Fig. 8. (a) and Fig. 10), which can be attributed to their strong hydrophobicity. The Fmoc capping group and the two tryptophan residues remained consistently closer to the bilayer and their distances were relatively more stable compared to the arginines and NH_2 group of Priscilicidin (Table 3. and Fig. S5.). The insertions of Priscilicidin's residues into the bilayer (Fig. 11. (a & b)) were less frequent when compared to the residues of Indolicidin (Fig. 11. (c & d)). The Fmoc moiety embedded deeper into the lipid bilayer and interacted with the hydrocarbon chains at 140 – 150 ns and 170 – 200 ns. The deep

Fig. 8. (a) Number of contacts between each residue with a MO bilayer for both Indolicidin and Priscilicidin. Calculations based on 200 ns simulation. Indolicidin are colour coded in purple and Priscilicidin in orange, (b) Radius of gyration (Rg) of Indolicidin and Priscilicidin, (c) and (d) Root mean square fluctuations for both Indolicidin and Priscilicidin, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3

Minimum distances between each residue of the peptides and the MO bilayer. The distances were calculated as averages from 40 ns to 200 ns of the trajectory.

Peptides	Residues	Minimum distances (nm)	STD (\pm nm)
Indolicidin	Ile1	0.23	0.043
	Leu2	0.21	0.037
	Pro3	0.25	0.07
	Trp4	0.22	0.019
	Lys5	0.37	0.13
	Trp6	0.23	0.032
	Pro7	0.24	0.056
	Trp8	0.2	0.02
	Trp9	0.2	0.02
	Pro10	0.21	0.02
	Trp11	0.22	0.015
	Arg12	0.26	0.1
	Arg13	0.31	0.096
	NH ₂	0.4	0.19
Priscilicidin	Fmoc	0.21	0.02
	Trp1	0.2	0.019
	Trp2	0.21	0.022
	Arg3	0.24	0.062
	Arg4	0.29	0.1
	NH ₂	0.43	0.18

penetration of the Fmoc moiety could likely explain higher encapsulation efficiency for Priscilicidin compared to Indolicidin in MO cubosomes. This observation suggests that the residues of Priscilicidin were primarily interacting at the interface region, except for the Fmoc moiety. Like Indolicidin, the positions of the arginines throughout the trajectory and the snapshots taken in the Priscilicidin-MO system demonstrated that the arginine residues preferred the aqueous region rather than the lipid bilayer (Fig. 11. (b)).

Previously, it has been suggested that a protein that penetrates superficially into a bilayer will generate more membrane bending than those that embed deep into the hydrophobic region [88,89]. The snapshots that were taken from the simulations revealed that Priscilicidin had resulted in significant bilayer bending, particularly at 80 ns and 120 ns of the simulation (Fig. 10. (c & d)). Accordingly, the Z-coordinates of the COM of Priscilicidin (Fig. 11. (a)) demonstrated that the peptide was primarily interacting at the interfacial region. No significant penetrations into the hydrocarbon chains were observed prior to \sim 140 ns. When the insertion of the Fmoc moiety of Priscilicidin eventually occurred, the membrane bending effect became less apparent (Fig. 10. (e)). In contrast, the tryptophan residues of Indolicidin were consistently inserted deep into the bilayer (Fig. 11. (c)) throughout the simulation. Therefore, the membrane curving effects induced by Indolicidin (Fig. 9) were less evident than Priscilicidin.

The average Rg of Priscilicidin interacting with the MO bilayer was

Fig. 9. Snapshots of Indolicidin's trajectory obtained at (a) 0 ns, (b) 40 ns, (c) 80 ns, (d) 120 ns, (e) 160 ns, and (f) 200 ns timepoints. The MO lipid bilayer is presented with the headgroup region in blue and the hydrophobic chains in grey. Indolicidin is presented in sticks, and coloured based on the residue (isoleucine – blue, leucine – pink, lysine – white, proline –yellow, tryptophan –orange, arginine – cyan, NH₂ – green). The tryptophans are thickened in orange for visualisation purposes. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

lower (0.64 ± 0.046 nm) than that of Indolicidin (0.78 ± 0.03 nm), suggesting it is more compact than that of Indolicidin and consistent with the small number of amino acid residues in Priscilicidin (Fig. 8. (b)). In contrast to Indolicidin, the Rg of Priscilicidin was not as consistent, implying that Priscilicidin may have undergone multiple structural changes during the simulation. Some sharp increases were observed at several time points throughout the trajectory, specifically at 44, 161, 163, 169, 173, 188, 194, and 197 ns. Significant drops were also observed at 61, 93, 160, 170, and 189 ns of the simulation. Additionally, the structure of Priscilicidin became less compact towards the end of trajectory, where its Rg was similar to those of Indolicidin. The RMSF data confirms that Priscilicidin has a higher level of flexibility compared to Indolicidin (Fig. 8. (d)).

3.5. Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity of a selection of AMP-cubosome formulations was tested against *E. coli* (gram-negative) and MRSA (gram-positive) bacterial strains and results compared to the corresponding unloaded AMP. Antimicrobial activity was tested in either Milli-Q water or salt (NaCl, 150 mM), due to the much higher peptide loading achieved in cubosomes in the presence of salt. Cubosomes were loaded with

AMPs as described in the Materials and Methods section, and samples tested at a range of concentrations between 5 and 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, both at the expected minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and lower levels. The antibacterial activity of AMP-cubosome formulations in 150 mM NaCl are presented in Fig. 12; data in Milli-Q water are presented in Fig. S6. Samples were tested for their activity in duplicate with triplicate readings of each duplicate sample; the average inhibition % is presented in each case.

The antibacterial activity of Indolicidin dissolved in NaCl against *E. coli* is presented in Fig. 12. (a); the calculated MIC value of 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ is in agreement with previous studies of Indolicidin in water [28]. Encapsulation of Indolicidin in MO cubosomes at 1 or 2 mol% resulted in a decrease in antibacterial activity at all concentrations studied. While increasing the loading from 1 to 2 mol% increased the activity, overall cubosome encapsulation resulted in a lower antimicrobial activity compared to the free peptide. The activity of Indolicidin (free peptide and cubosome loaded) in Milli-Q water was similar to that in salt against *E. coli* (Fig. S6. (a)). Cubosome encapsulation also generally resulted in a decrease in activity. One exception was cubosomes loaded with 2 mol % Indolicidin in Milli-Q water at higher concentrations (20 – 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) which displayed a high antimicrobial activity (~85 % inhibition at 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). While further studies are needed to assess this effect, it may

Fig. 10. Snapshots of Priscilicidin's trajectory obtained at (a) 0 ns, (b) 40 ns, (c) 80 ns, (d) 120 ns, (e) 160 ns, and (f) 200 ns timepoints. The MO lipid bilayer is presented with the headgroup region in blue and the hydrophobic chains in grey. Priscilicidin is presented in sticks and coloured based on its residue (Fmoc – red, tryptophan – orange, arginine – cyan, NH_2 – green). The Fmoc moiety is thickened in red for visualisation purposes. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

reflect the lower loading of Indolicidin in cubosomes in Milli-Q water and the increase in the relative amount of free peptide.

Against the gram-positive bacteria MRSA, Indolicidin in salt solution showed a MIC of $60 \mu\text{g/mL}$ (Fig. 12. (c)) within the range of measured values from previous studies [28]. Incorporation of Indolicidin in MO salt cubosomes (at either 1 or 2 mol%) resulted in no observed improvement in antimicrobial activity compared to that of free Indolicidin at low concentrations ($5 - 20 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and a reduced level of activity at higher concentrations ($40 - 60 \mu\text{g/mL}$), suggesting this combination is ineffective against gram-positive MRSA. Similarly, Indolicidin incorporated into MO in Milli-Q water at both 1 and 2 mol% illustrated poor activity against MRSA (Fig. S6. (c)).

The antibacterial activity of Priscilicidin in salt (Fig. 12. (b)) against the gram-negative bacterial strain *E. coli* (O157:H7 strain) was relatively low. A previous study has shown higher activity of Priscilicidin against the *E. coli* NCTC 10418 strain with a MIC value of $\sim 60 \mu\text{g/mL}$ [54]. Incorporating Priscilicidin at 1 mol% in salt solution demonstrated enhanced antibacterial activity at all concentrations ($5 - 60 \mu\text{g/mL}$) compared to free Priscilicidin in salt solution. However, increasing the loading to 2 mol% reduced the activity compared to that at 1 mol%. As

cubosomes loaded with either 1 or 2 mol% Priscilicidin are structurally very similar, we are not currently able to explain this result. The antibacterial activity of Priscilicidin in Milli-Q water was similar to that found in salt (Fig. S6. (b)). At lower Priscilicidin concentrations ($5 - 20 \mu\text{g/mL}$) encapsulation in cubosomes in Milli-Q water did not improve the antimicrobial activity relative to that of free Priscilicidin in Milli-Q water. However, at higher concentrations of peptide ($40 - 60 \mu\text{g/mL}$), cubosome encapsulation resulted in enhanced antimicrobial activity, with the % inhibition increasing from $\sim 34\%$ to $\sim 67\%$ at $40 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and from $\sim 36\%$ to $\sim 74\%$ at $60 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Increasing the loading of Priscilicidin to 2 mol% did not improve the antibacterial activity of the peptide against gram-negative *E. coli*.

Against gram-positive MRSA, Priscilicidin in salt solution displayed strong antibacterial activity, with a calculated MIC reported of only $5 \mu\text{g/mL}$ (Fig. 12. (d)). Encapsulation in cubosomes reduced the activity relative to that of the free peptide. Priscilicidin dissolved in Milli-Q water had similar activity to that in salt solution (Fig. S6. (d)), but encapsulating Priscilicidin in Milli-Q water containing cubosomes was also shown to be ineffective compared to free Priscilicidin.

The antimicrobial activity of Indolicidin and Priscilicidin

Fig. 11. The distance between centre of mass of the peptide residues and the centre of mass of the glycerol headgroup of the top lipid bilayer; (a) Fmoc and Priscilicidin tryptophan's, (b) Priscilicidin arginine's (c) Indolicidin tryptophan's (d) Indolicidin arginine's. A negative value corresponds to a deeper penetration into the MO bilayer.

encapsulated in MO cubosomes may be related to their mechanism of action. The antibacterial mechanism of action of Indolicidin is not yet fully understood but is proposed to be linked to a combination of membrane interactions and intracellular targets. Indolicidin has been shown to inhibit the synthesis of DNA in *E. coli* cells resulting in filamentation [49–53,90]. In addition, Indolicidin has been shown to permeate across the outer membrane in gram-negative bacteria and subsequently disrupt the cytoplasmic membrane via the formation of discrete channels or the induction of disorder within the bilayer by changes to the chain packing. However, it has been proposed that the relatively small size and disordered structure of Indolicidin render it unable to span a bilayer, compared to α -helical or β -stranded AMPs. Rather, Indolicidin may need to form dimers or small aggregates to induce the disruptive membrane effect [49,53]. In agreement with our data, previous CD and MD simulations have shown that Indolicidin is preferentially located at the interfacial region of POPC and PPG lipid bilayers [50,51]. This could potentially restrict the motion of the tryptophans, reducing the peptide's ability to self-aggregate, which may, at least partially, explain the reduced activity of Indolicidin encapsulated into cubosomes. This may also explain the increased antimicrobial activity observed for Indolicidin (2 mol% in MO cubosomes) in Milli-Q water against *E. coli* at higher concentrations driven by the increased percentage of free peptide (Fig. S6. (a)). We note that the cubic architecture of the cubosomes was disrupted at this peptide loading; subsequent release of the free peptide would facilitate the formation of dimers and small aggregates and result in the observed increase in antimicrobial activity.

The antimicrobial and antifungal activity of Priscilicidin has also been shown to result from its self assembly into viscoelastic hydrogels [54]. Using MD simulations, the peptide was shown to form oligomers and nanofibrils in water through intermolecular pi-stacking of the aromatic and hydrophobic Fmoc groups in the central core [54]. MD simulations in this study demonstrated that the Fmoc within the peptide sequence drives interactions with the MO bilayer resulting in high measured encapsulation efficiency of Priscilicidin in MO. This is likely to

significantly reduce the peptide's ability to self-assemble resulting in a reduction in antimicrobial activity. In general, all experimental data support the reduced activity of both these AMPs when encapsulated. We note that Priscilicidin (1 mol% in MO cubosomes) did show some evidence of improved antibacterial activity against gram-negative bacteria. However, this effect was not observed at 2 mol% loading and more studies are needed across a wide range of bacterial strains to confirm this effect.

Several recent studies have proposed that cubosome-mediated delivery of antimicrobial compounds results from interaction and uptake of the cubosome into the bacteria, rather than release of the antimicrobial agent [26,91,92]. For gram-negative bacteria, a two-stage internalisation mechanism of MO cubosomes was proposed via (1) fusion of the cubosome lipid bilayer with the outer lipid membrane of the gram-negative bacterium *E. coli*, followed by (2) subsequent diffusion of the constituent cubosome lipids and encapsulated antimicrobial compound into the bacterium [92]. For gram-positive bacteria, including *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*, MO cubosomes initially attached to the outer bacterial surface, subsequently acting as reservoirs and releasing the encapsulated bioactives through diffusion across the thick peptidoglycan layer [92]. This mechanistic understanding was used to explain the significant improvement in antimicrobial efficacy for cubosome-mediated delivery of hydrophobic antibiotics such as rifampicin and fusidic acid, which exhibited relatively slow-release (~82 % and 12 % over 72 h respectively), against *E. coli* [92]. We note that a similar delivery mechanism is plausible for Indolicidin and Priscilicidin which have significant hydrophobic character.

Recently, a “diffusion to capture” model was derived to explain the antimicrobial activity of compounds with low and high permeation [93]. The model assumes that the activity of an antimicrobial agent is correlated with the permeability of the drug, encapsulation of compounds with low permeation, such as novobiocin, in cubosomes results in increased antibacterial activity. However, the encapsulation strategy was found to be ineffective for compounds with high permeation such as meropenem by hindering the rate of transport to bacteria [93,94]. Data

Fig. 12. Measured OD values calculated as % inhibition relative to the concentration of AMP against two bacterial strains for unloaded, 1 mol% (1) and 2 mol% (2) loaded peptides. (a) Indolicidin in salt samples against *E. coli*, (b) Priscilicidin in salt samples against *E. coli*, (c) Indolicidin in salt samples against MRSA and (d) Priscilicidin in salt samples tested against MRSA. (Salt; 150 mM NaCl). In cases where there are no error bars, the error bars are smaller than the symbol.

presented in this study are, therefore, consistent with this model as both Indolicidin and Priscilicidin have relatively high permeability as free drugs and demonstrated reduced activity when encapsulated. This suggests that the cubosome encapsulation strategy may not necessarily improve the rate of delivery to bacteria for antimicrobial compounds of high permeation efficiency. However, we note that encapsulation in cubosomes does offer additional advantages such as protection of AMPs from enzymatic degradation [41] and ability to deliver antimicrobials to intracellular infections [24].

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the use of cubosome lipid nanoparticles as nanocarriers for the antimicrobial peptide Indolicidin and its derivative, the ultra-short peptide fragment Priscilicidin. While the encapsulation efficiency of Priscilicidin in MO cubosomes was higher than that of Indolicidin, loading of both peptides resulted in a disruption to the cubic nanostructure even at low peptide loading. Addition of 150 mM NaCl to screen the cationic charge of both peptides was shown to both increase the encapsulation efficiency and assist with retention of the cubosome nanostructure. A combination of CD spectroscopy and MD simulations showed that encapsulation resulted in minor changes to the peptide secondary structure. MD simulations confirmed that interactions between the peptides and the MO bilayer were driven by both hydrophobic tryptophan residues and, for Priscilicidin, the Fmoc group. For both

peptides, encapsulation into cubosomes was generally associated with a reduction of antimicrobial activity against both gram-negative and gram-positive bacterial strains. This may be correlated to the mechanism of action of the peptide, the self-assembly of both peptides is critical to their antimicrobial efficacy and this could be hindered by encapsulation. Moreover, based on a recent diffusion to capture model we suggest cubosome encapsulation may not work well for these AMPs which display relatively high permeation across the bacterial membrane. The results suggest that, while cubosomes may be an effective strategy for enhancing the antimicrobial activity of some antibiotic compounds, this may be restricted to compounds of naturally low membrane permeation and to compounds whose mechanism of action does not involve self-assembly and the formation of aggregates. In order to design more effective nanocarriers for antimicrobials, further studies are, therefore, needed to understand the mechanism of action of potential antibiotic compounds more fully, and how this is impacted by cubosome encapsulation.

5. Declaration of Generative artificial intelligence

Generative artificial intelligence tool ChatGPT was employed during the preparation of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and revised the content as needed, and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Biserka Lakić: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Chia Beh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Sampa Sarkar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Sue-Lyn Yap:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Priscila Cardoso:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Celine Valery:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Andrew Hung:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nykola C. Jones:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Søren Vrønning Hoffmann:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Ewan W. Blanch:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Brendan Dyett:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Charlotte E. Conn:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: [Biserka Lakić reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper].

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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